

LAND COVER ANALYSIS IN THE YANGTZE RIVER BASIN FOR DETECTION OF WETLAND AGRICULTURE AND URBAN DYNAMICS IN WUHAN AREA (CHINA)

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ABSTRACT

This study presents environmental analysis of the Yangtze River Basin, Wuhan region of central China, performed using machine learning (ML) methods of Remote Sensing (RS) data classification. The workflow is performed using Geographic Resources Analysis Support System (GRASS) Geographic Information System (GIS) scripting software for processing Landsat images by two approaches: unsupervised clustering and supervised ML algorithms. Six Landsat images were taken biennially in autumn from 2013 to 2023 to detect wetland changes in the Wuhan area. This article demonstrates the application of ML in GIS for analysis of landscape dynamics to detect changes in riverine and lacustrine areas around the Yangtze River.

RÉSUMÉ: Analyse de la végétation du bassin du fleuve Yangtze pour identifier l'agriculture des zones humides et la dynamique urbaine autour de la région de Wuhan (Chine).

Cette étude présente une analyse environnementale du fleuve Yangtze, Chine, réalisée à l'aide de méthodes d'apprentissage automatique de classification des images. Le flux de travail est effectué à l'aide du logiciel de script SIG GRASS pour le traitement des images Landsat par deux approches: le clustering et les algorithmes automatiques. Six images ont été prises de 2013 à 2023 pour détecter les changements dans les zones humides de la région de Wuhan. Cet article a montré l'apprentissage automatique en cartographie pour l'analyse de la dynamique du paysage dans les zones fluviales et lacustres autour du fleuve Yangtze.

REZUMAT: Analiza acoperirii terenurilor pentru Bazinul Fluviului Yangtze pentru detectarea agriculturii zonelor umede și a dinamicii urbane în jurul zonei Wuhan (China).

Acest studiu prezintă analiza de mediu a râului Yangtze, China centrală, efectuată folosind metode de învățare automată de clasificare a datelor RS. Fluxul de lucru este realizat folosind software-ul de scripting GRASS GIS pentru procesarea imaginilor Landsat prin două abordări: clustering nesupravegheat și algoritmi ML supravegheați. Au fost realizate șase imagini Landsat cu un interval de timp de 2 ani din 2013 până în 2023 pentru a detecta schimbările în zonele umede din zona Wuhan. Acest articol a arătat aplicarea în cartografie pentru analiza dinamicii peisajului în zonele fluviale și lacustre din jurul râului Yangtze.

INTRODUCTION

Wuhan, the capital of Hubei Province in China, is home to a key wetland resource of the Yangtze River. The basin of this river makes Wuhan one of the major international wetland urban areas. Sustainable development of this urban wetland city plays an important role in helping to maintain urban wetlands. In order to protect and manage wetlands in the Yangtze River Basin, it is essential to comprehend how wetlands grow and change over time. Therefore, wetland mapping over time is essential for wetland conservation and maintenance of healthy riverine and lacustrine ecology in central China. At the same time, Wuhan is also experiencing urban sprawl, which has an impact on the riverine and lacustrine ecosystems. With population growth, global economic challenges and the restructuring of urban spaces, urban expansion is becoming a major concern in many countries around the world.

Accurate wetland mapping is therefore essential for this region, which is notable for an important environment and how it is experiencing recent urban growth. A particular example of urban growth is China, where the expansion of urban agglomerations results from the unprecedented economic development that has occurred in recent decades (Long et al., 2023; Lan et al., 2021; Guan et al., 2020; Li and Li, 2019). Analysis of urban growth and associated changes in landscape models is very useful for urban planning, management and policy development for sustainable development. To date, the use of geographic information systems (GIS) and remote sensing data for visualization of land cover change are the most effective research methods for mapping. This is found in many research papers using satellite data (Amankulova et al., 2023; Lebaut and Manceau, 2015; Kana and Etouna, 2006).

In the past decades, satellite images have been used to track urban growth and land use change through their availability, spatial resolution and time coverage. Information that can be extracted from satellite images is useful for mapping, statistical analysis and modelling. Satellite image processing methods can be broadly classified as undirected and GIS-guided classification. While traditional methods rely mainly on the use of predefined commands available in existing GIS, advanced methods present the use of machine learning (“machine learning”) programming algorithms for automated image processing. This article presents a new methodology, which proposes the implementation of several methods for classification of a series of 6 satellite images covering the Wuhan region, China, between 2013 and 2023.

In this study, we use machine learning methods using the GRASS GIS software and its four machine learning algorithms applied to satellite image processing. The objective is to detect changes in land cover types around the Yangtze River, central China, for urban sprawl monitoring in Wuhan using six Landsat 8-9 OLI/TIRS satellite images. The challenge of having accurate information on the development of urban areas is important for readers of the journal. This paper aims to evaluate how these land use changes are perceived in Wuhan using GRASS GIS programming methods applied to the processing of satellite images.

The study area is located between 112°38'05.03"E-115°02'28.21"E and 29°13'58.98"N-31°21'35.86"N (Fig. 1), along the Yangtze River and includes a heterogeneous landscape mosaic of the city of Wuhan and its surroundings, Hubei Province, China. Here, the climatic and topographical conditions of the Wuhan region are strongly affected by the Yangtze River which flows through Hunan Province dividing the city into two with varied landscapes (Cao et al., 2022). The climate near Wuhan along the Yangtze is a humid subtropical monsoon climate from the north with abundant rainfall. Total annual precipitation of 1,315 mm ranges from 20 mm in December to over 220 mm in July (Dai et al., 2023). The average daily temperature ranges from 4°C to 30°C (Fu et al., 2008). These climates favor agriculture. The effects of climate and topographical context around Wuhan, along the Yangtze River, affect vegetation types and influence preferred locations of human settlements.

Figure 1: Location of study area.
Source: author. Software: GMT.

Participating in China's unprecedented economic growth since the 1970s, Wuhan is a rapidly developing city that dynamically expands into neighboring regions (Fan et al., 2022). Expansion models of this area have been discussed in numerous articles (Tong et al., 2019; He et al., 2018; Hu et al., 2015). Wuhan's controlled urbanization is beneficial to the region: as the capital of Hunan Province, it supports social and economic development, improves the efficiency of the land use system and promotes sustainable development. By providing workplaces and developed infrastructure, the Wuhan agglomeration improves the standard of living of its inhabitants (Huang et al., 2022). The difference in built-up areas and population density varies significantly in central and peripheral parts of the city. This is certainly changing the ecological situation of the city and its surroundings due to different environmental pressures. In addition, UNESCO's ranking of Wuhan as a "creative city" in 2014 certainly has an effect on its development because it increases the attractiveness of the city for newcomers and tourists.

The thematic aspect and contextual elements related to the choice of the Wuhan region for this analysis are related to the rapid urbanization of this city and its surrounding area. Uncontrolled urbanization causes a series of environmental problems including fragmentation of the landscape, land cover change (Tan et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2020), deterioration of lake and river water quality, (Hu et al., 2023; Dou et al., 2022) and a loss of agricultural land as it is replaced by urban areas (Yuan et al., 2019; Zeng et al., 2015). To monitor urban dynamics in the Wuhan region, many studies have been undertaken to map urban growth. The main approach of these studies was to use satellite images (Zhang et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2020) and GIS (Deng et al., 2023; Xing et al., 2023; Zhou et al., 2023; Geng et al., 2022).

The simulated environmental models reported in this work indicate changes in recent landscapes and environmental conditions of Wuhan (2020) compared to the previous state (since the 1980s), which is explained by the urban expansion of Wuhan as the rapidly developing capital of Hubei province (Ding and Chen, 2022). In this respect, the urban dynamics of Wuhan require a mapping for the development of ecological protection. These objectives can be effectively achieved with advanced image processing and geospatial analysis tools. Other environmental problems are caused by the proximity of the river, because wastewater discharges increase the pollution of soil through the water. As a result, pollutants are transferred to plants, causing negative environmental effects.

There are many issues related to the environmental dynamics of the Wuhan region, and the most important one is the following. Urban expansion in the period 2013-2023 was faster than that of other cities in central and eastern China due to rapid urbanization of Wuhan which outstrips other cities. The reason for this is the dynamic socio-economic development of the city, which attracts many new residents to Wuhan. So the city was chosen to become an urban model for the development of central China and oriented land use changes, since Wuhan is a representative example of rapid urban sprawl in China.

In this study, we use machine learning methods implemented in the GRASS GIS driven by remote sensing data to analyze urban growth and landscape dynamics in Wuhan along the Yangtze River. Land cover type data are derived from relevant studies (Wang and Wang, 2022; Teng et al., 2016) and adapted to the current study area extent. In terms of values derived from the pixel spectral reflectance, the types of earth coverage are visualized on maps for the period 2013 to 2023 with a time interval of 2 years. Machine learning processes satellite images using directed classification methods and training data (Zheng et al., 2023; Mountrakis and Heydari, 2023; Nagaraj and Kumar, 2023).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Remote sensing (RS) data are useful for mapping land cover changes and landscape dynamics in the riverine and lacustrine environments. Therefore, Landsat images were used for spatial analysis. The geodetic characteristics of satellite images are as follows. The original data are in Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) projection, zone 49, reference and ellipsoid WGS84. The technical characteristics are as follows. Landsat collection category is T1, collection number 2, NGL station identifier. Image sensor ID is OLI TIRS, Satellite ID 8 for all images except the 2023 image which has Satellite ID 9; data are shown in figure 2 and include the following six Landsat 8-9 OLI/TIRS scenes: 1. Landsat Scene ID LC81230392013324LGN01, collected on 2013/11/20; 2. Landsat Scene ID LC81230392015298LGN01, collected on 2015/10/25; 3. Landsat Scene ID LC81230392017303LGN00, collected on 2017/10/30; 4. Landsat Scene ID LC81230392019293LGN00, collected on 2019/10/20; 5. Landsat Scene ID LC81230392021314LGN00, collected on 2021/11/10; 6. Landsat Scene ID LC91230392023296LGN00, collected on 2023/10/23.

Figure 2: Satellite data: Images 8-9 Landsat 8-9 OLI/TIRS covering the Yangtze River region, Wuhan, Central China. Data: USGS. The figures are in the original natural colors. Image compilation: author.

The classification methods available in the free GIS software GRASS GIS allowed us to characterize the urban sprawl of Wuhan by characterizing a class of built urban areas. The ML algorithms include Decision Tree Classifier, Random Forest (RF) Regressor, Gradient Boosting Classifier and Support Vector Machine Classifier. The general modules of GRASS GIS used in this work have used the following modules. First, the data was imported into GRASS GIS using the GDAL library using «r.import» and mapped. The module “g.region” was used to define the boundary of the Wuhan geographic area using the coordinates of the Landsat raster bands (UTM, zone 49). Then, band groups of the Landsat images were created for each included year from 2013 to 2023, including multispectral channels and excluding panchromatic channels that were not required. After preprocessing the data, the next step included undirected classification using aggregation and maximum likelihood methods.

Here we describe the implementation of a non-directed classification function (i.cluster, equivalent to k-means), whose resulting classes are then assigned to pixels via a metric based on maximum likelihood (i.maxlik). This is the result of this classification which is then compared to 4 directed machine learning classification methods (Decision tree; Random Forest; Gradient Boosting and SVM). The defined land use classes are: 1) water bodies (river, Yangtze, lakes); 2) agricultural, agricultural and cultivated lands; 3) urban built-up areas and artificial surfaces; 4) forest; 5) scrubland; 6) wetlands; 7) grasslands; 8) bare land.

Then, the undirected classification was carried out by the module “i.maxlik” using the following code: “i.maxlik group=L8_2013 subgroup=res_30m signaturefile=cluster_L8_2013 output=L8_2013_cluster_classes reject=L8_2013_cluster_reject” As can be seen, the algorithm uses the signature file created in the previous clustering step. The results of the classification are shown in figure 3. The “reject” function evaluates the percentage of pixels that have been correctly classified. This assessment of the accuracy of satellite images classified by the module “i.maxlik” was performed by the authors and is shown in figure 4. Here, the accuracy of the classification is assessed by threshold levels determining the confidence level of the correct assignment of each classified cell. These classes indicate the probability categories for rejection. The map display was visualized using a combination of modules “d. mon”, “r.colors”, “d. rast” and “d. legend”. The models were developed using four directed classification algorithms: the decision tree classifier (‘Decision Tree Classifier’), the random forest regressor (‘Random Forest Regressor’), the gradient-reinforced classifier (Gradient Boosting Classifier) and the Support Vector Machine Classifier (‘Support Vector Machine’). The series of maps showing land cover types in the Wuhan area, generated using the described method, is presented and discussed in the following section.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The total of simulated land cover types is estimated in number of pixels per class and ranges as presented in table 1. A pixel of the Landsat scene corresponds to a 30*30 m cell. The area occupied can therefore be calculated using the multispectral band resolution information from Landsat images (Fig. 3).

A relatively stable situation is noted for Class 1 land-use bodies of water (Yangtze river, lakes) that demonstrate a rather sustainable situation with pixels fluctuating slightly from 1337 in 2013 to 1347 in 2023, which corresponds to non-significant changes in the areas covered by water bodies from 40,110 m² to 40,410 m² respectively. Slight changes might be caused by the seasonal environmental effects and climate-related issues. The area occupied by Class 2 (agricultural and cultivated lands) shows a slight increase from 1,337 to 1,347 pixels, from 40,110 m² to 40,410 m². Significant fluctuations in 2015 (1231 pixels) and 1217 (1206 pixels) may indicate a year of local processes causing agricultural land to fluctuate

Class 3 (urban built-up areas and artificial surfaces) increased by 15% from 1034 to 1208 pixels, or 31,020 m² to 36,240 m². Class 4 (forest) shows a continuous decrease with the number of pixels decreasing from 792 in 2013 to 376 in 2023, which corresponds to a decrease of more than half of the forest area from 23,760 m² to 11,280 m². But it is above all the coverage of the soil by natural vegetation (maquis, class 5 which includes vegetation types other than forest, e.g., thickets). That is the most significant decrease in surface area, with a number of pixels decreasing from 1726 in 2013 to 1195 in 2023, a reduction of 30% in vegetation coverage of land in this class, which decreases from 51,780 m² to 35,850 m². Such a fall is due to the use of natural land earlier occupied by various types of vegetation such as shrubs for agriculture, and reflects rise of land used for agricultural needs in Hubei Province.

A comparison was done using numerical analysis of data (Tab. 1) revealing differences between classes 5 and 2. It indicates the increase in agricultural, and cultivated land. Fluctuations in Class 6 (wetlands) with a gradual increase from 716 pixels in 2013 to 1045 in 2021 followed by a decrease in 2023 to 817 pixels are explained by environmental and climatic processes (temperature variations and precipitation which leads to the increase in wetlands and seasonally flooded areas). Land use class 7 (grasslands including land used for pastures and grazing) indicates a large increase in area from 580 pixels earlier to 903 last year. Land use Class 8 (bare and unoccupied lands) variations show a significant increase from 428 pixels in 2013 to 688 pixels in 2023, which is related to building at the urban margins (Tab. 1).

Figure 3: Landsat images classified using the “maximum likelihood” method by automated clustering. Class notations: 1) water bodies (river, Yangtze River, lakes); 2) agricultural, agricultural and cultivated land; 3) urban built-up areas and artificial surfaces; 4) forest; 5) maquis; 6) wetlands; 7) grasslands; 8) bare and unoccupied land. Source: author.

Table 1: Distribution of pixels by changing classes according to the year calculated by the classifier “i.maxlike”, GRASS SIG. Classes: 1) water bodies (river, Yangtze river, lakes); 2) agricultural, agricultural and cultivated land; 3) urban built-up areas and artificial surfaces; 4) forest; 5) maquis; 6) wetlands; 7) grasslands; 8) bare and unoccupied land.

Year	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3	Class 4	Class 5	Class 6	Class 7	Class 8
2013	508	1337	1034	792	1726	716	580	428
2015	390	1231	1078	791	1164	941	985	546
2017	430	1206	1087	674	1175	980	980	696
2019	850	1309	1162	647	1024	869	844	517
2021	456	1336	1173	567	1067	1045	883	695
2023	709	1347	1208	376	1195	817	903	688

The accuracy assessment that evaluates the pixels correctly assigned to the land cover classes is evaluated by classification confidence level thresholds, as shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: Evaluation of the accuracy of satellite images.
Maps show pixel rejection probability classes.

The raster map in figure 4 shows the results of the rejection threshold calculation. This is the result of a chi-square test on each discriminant at different confidence levels. The calculation is done to determine at what confidence level each cell is classified and categorized. The map rejection threshold layer contains the index of a calculated confidence level for each classified cell in the classified image. Here, confidence intervals are pre-defined and the rejection map should be interpreted as minimum values = retain (assigned to the correct class) and maximum values = reject, that is a low probability (high rejection index). Thus, the wrong classification is indicated by the colors black and dark blue while the correct classification is indicated by the color orange. The calculation indicates the percentage of pixels that are associated with the target class correctly. The rejection probability indicates the number of pixels that are rejected below the threshold levels of confidence. This level determines at what confidence level each cell is classified (i.e., categorized to the target land cover class).

Figure 5 shows spatial patterns of the gap between land cover types (river streams, lakes and urban areas and settlements around Wuhan) classified by maximum likelihood algorithms and the decision tree classifier. In the latter, the erroneous assignment of pixels to the class of agricultural crop fields and urban spaces is lower than that of the non-directed classification. The spectral reflectance changes as vegetation becomes active and is stronger when vegetation is abundant. Therefore, spectral reflectance has detected declining vegetation which is shown in yellow, while healthy vegetation is shown in red (Fig. 5). The difference

between the two approaches may be due to different ML methods of assignment of pixels to the target class. The values of the pixels assigned to a specific class derived from machine learning and simulated by the DT Classifier approach are calculated using the drive polygons derived from the non-directed classification. Their recognition is therefore more precise than the undirected classification.

The machine learning approach with supervised classification provides better estimates of land cover types and urban/plant fractions in GRASS GIS algorithms than using a non-directed classification. In doing so, the maps in figures 5 to 8 are based on existing formation polygons to quantify these relatively small models of land cover types that visualize various classes of land cover, including the most dynamic areas of urban areas and agricultural fields. The maps produced in figures 5 to 8 show quantified changes in natural surfaces, urban landscapes around Wuhan, watercourses and wetlands. In addition, maps generated using supervised machine learning classified data or landscape dynamics predictions are a key advantage over traditional image classification methods.

Figure 5: Landsat images processed using a ML method using a Decision Tree Classifier algorithm for supervised classification that includes training dataset.

The algorithm of random forest (RF) outperforms maps in terms of mapping accuracy through more distinct differences between classes. Besides, it is well aligned with results obtained from land cover change variations and urban growth around Wuhan: Decrease in areas occupied by maquis or shrubland which refers to plant formations made of shrubs and small trees (Class 5) and wetlands or seasonally flooded areas (Class 5). In Class 6, the increase in areas occupied by urban built-up areas and artificial surfaces (Class 3) and agricultural land, agricultural and cultivated (Class 2) as well as slight variations of other land use classes, related to climate and environmental impact factors. In addition, there are uncertainties in the automated pixel grouping that is visible on figure 3 and visualized in the

precision maps of figure 4. However, The use of directed classification eliminates these errors by more precisely assigning pixels to different classes. As noted in previous studies (Brown de Colstoun et al., 2003), the decision tree classifier provides a more realistic approach to land cover classifications needed to better estimate classes with assigned pixels (Fig. 5).

The result of the random forest regression classification (Random Forest) is shown in figure 6. The results indicate that the use of this algorithm coupled to the 30 m resolution multispectral bands of Landsat had the best performance compared to other machine learning models, respectively. The maps in figure 6 also shows a very large spatial heterogeneity in the evolution of urban and vegetation areas. Compared to other approaches, the random forest algorithm is general in nature and applies to classification of various types of land cover, including many types of vegetation. Thus, this algorithm is widely used to estimate certain environmental land-use properties and individual biophysical characteristics of the plant cover such as biomass and vegetation cover rate (Fig. 6).

Figure 6: Landsat images processed using the machine learning method using the Random Forest Regressor algorithm for supervised classification. Figure creation: author.

The modeling results using the gradient boosting approach are shown in figure 7. The gradient boosting algorithm is a type of machine learning that implies that the combination of the next best model and the previous model minimizes the prediction error (Shirazi et al., 2024). The effectiveness of this approach has been tested in previous studies on satellite image processing with examples of Landsat (Godinho et al., 2016) or WorldView-3 (Shendryk et al., 2020) and proved that the gradient boost minimizes the classification error through the defined target classification results. As the change results indicate that the forest and shrub areas in 2013 were partially transformed to other classes during the period 2013–2023. On the contrary, the urban areas of Wuhan and its suburbs have been developing in the past ten years.

Figure 7: Landsat images processed using machine learning method “gradient boosting” classifier algorithm for supervised classification.

The mapping of Classes carried out by the classification using the “gradient boosting” approach from four satellite images acquired between 2013 and 2023 allows an analysis of the interannual effects on the types of land cover of the Wuhan study area (Fig. 7). The comparison of spatial occupation of vegetation and urban areas is ensured by the comparability of the maps. The Support Vector Machine (SVM) approach (Fig. 8) aims to solve a complex classification by an optimal pixel transformation that determines the boundaries between cell points based on predefined classes. The effectiveness of SVM is also presented in relevant works in which variables are retrieved from remote sensing data, including urban building detection (Mahmoud, 2021), shadow detection (Selvaraju et al., 2021) or cloudiness values (Joshi et al., 2019). The SVM algorithm is used to drive process-based models and can be very well applied to support satellite image classification.

In order to determine the application of the maximum likelihood method by automated clustering and machine learning to compare their approaches, for these scenes, we exploited the variations in the classification of pixels into classes using the maximum likelihood method (Fig. 3) decision tree classifier algorithm (Fig. 5) random forest algorithm (Fig. 6), gradient boosting classifier algorithm (Fig. 7) and Support Vector Machine – SVM algorithm (Fig. 8). In all cases, the calculation of classes according to these different methods relies directly on the difference between the surface reflectance in the spectral band per pixel. From the comparison of the resulting images it can be concluded that machine learning methods perform better than unsupervised methods. The derived values show the areas occupied by various land cover types around Wuhan for the period 2013-2023.

Figure 8: Landsat 8-9 OLI/TIRS images processed using machine learning method using “Support Vector Machine – SVM” algorithm for supervised classification.
Software: GRASS SIG.

The downside of maps generated using supervised machine learning (Figs. 5-8) is that they require more resources due to the need for labeled data. This also resulted in a longer processing time due to machine learning methods. For example, Support Vector Machine algorithms took more than 40 minutes to calculate one image, and the implementation of the Gradient Boosting Classifier took more than 30 minutes, while the MaxLike classification was performed in just a few seconds. Nevertheless, maps produced using machine learning (ML) methods provide more accurate results than traditional classification due to the algorithms of automate data processing.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, machine learning-based modeling of GRASS GIS software is used with Landsat 8-9 OLI/TIRS remote sensing data to identify and map changes in land cover types and urban areas in the rapidly growing densely populated Wuhan region and surrounding regions along the Yangtze River region, central China. At the ML algorithm level, the approaches capture and detect variations in the models used (decision tree classifier, random forest regressor, gradient boosting classifier, and support vector machine – SVM classifier).

The detected changes are visualized in a series of six maps showing the gradual increase in the extent of urban spaces with differences in the spatial structure of landscape models in the Wuhan region from 2013 to 2023. The landscape changes detected in the Wuhan region over the last ten years (2013-2023) have demonstrated the decrease of natural landscapes such as forests, grasslands, agricultural or cultivated land. Urban land, rural residential areas and building plots are increasing. Specifically,

these changes were notable in the landscape of the study area in the vicinity of Wuhan. Four main factors were identified as the drivers of these changes: anthropogenic practices affecting water and soil resources; urbanization and the reorganization of human settlements; rural development with new agricultural practices and changes introduced; environmental and climatic changes that have affected local topographical conditions such as soil erosion and desertification.

Such results illustrate the urbanization process in central China detected by processing remote sensing data using machine learning methods. In addition, the fact that the city has long developed according to a polycentric pattern due to the three old urban cores gathered in the conurbation has consequences on the way land use changes since the dynamics of urban sprawl varies in these areas. As a result, the intensity of urbanization is stronger in the suburbs or the construction of new buildings is more intensive than in the historic center which is related to the late but very fast development of the network of metro since 2013.

Future studies may consider using the proposed GRASS GIS techniques to map other neighbouring areas on satellite images, e.g., land use changes associated with the construction of the Caidian eco-city. Further studies could also increase the urban aspects of this research, going beyond the technical use of machine learning methods for satellite image processing. It is known that the city has a rigorous territorial planning and presents to its visitors a museum and urban center with a huge 3D model of the city. Therefore, future studies could continue this work by integrating urban surveys and remote sensing data. So the integrated use of satellite images with urban data can help answer questions about the correlation of urban dynamics and changes that are related to what is observed on satellite images.

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